

Performance Analysis of Acoustic Echo Cancellation using Adaptive Filter Algorithms with Rician Fading Channel

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ABSTRACT

In the realm of hands-free telephony and teleconferencing systems, ensuring high-quality, clear voice communication between participants in different locations is paramount. However, a significant challenge encountered is the presence of acoustic echo, which deteriorates the voice signal quality, obscuring the conversation content and potentially causing the loss of critical information. Acoustic echoes originate from sound wave reflections off walls and objects within a room. Addressing this issue, the primary goal for engineers is to eliminate acoustic echo, thereby achieving an echo-free communication environment. To this end, various adaptive filter algorithms have been developed and are under continuous refinement. This paper explores the effectiveness of acoustic echo cancellation by implementing and assessing different adaptive filter algorithms. Specifically, it evaluates the performance of the Least Mean Squares (LMS), Normalized Least Mean Squares (NLMS), and Unbiased Nonlinear Acoustic Echo Noise Reduction (UNANR) algorithms based on Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) metrics, utilizing MATLAB R2012a for simulation and analysis.

KEYWORDS: *Least Mean Squares, Speech enhancement, Normalized Least Mean Squares, AWGN channel, Adaptive noise cancellation*

1. INTRODUCTION

Speech has been the cornerstone of human communication since the dawn of civilization, serving as the most innate and natural means for exchanging thoughts and information. As we navigate through the evolution of communication, the essence of speech remains unchanged, embodying a vital link that connects individuals across different spheres of life. Central to the evaluation of speech signals is their quality and intelligibility, which together form the benchmark for assessing the effectiveness of verbal communication. Quality, a subjective attribute, reflects the perceived pleasantness or naturalness of speech, encapsulating the listener's auditory experience. On the other hand, intelligibility offers an objective yardstick, quantifying the percentage of words that listeners can accurately discern, thereby gauging the clarity of the communicated message.

In the context of speech enhancement, the focus extends beyond mere noise suppression, encompassing the reduction of reverberation and the segregation of overlapping speech signals. This broad

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spectrum of activities underlines the endeavor to refine both the intelligibility and quality of speech signals that have been compromised. Leveraging advanced signal processing techniques, speech enhancement aims to restore or even transcend the original attributes of speech, ensuring that communication remains clear, effective, and as close to its natural state as possible. Through these interventions, the goal is not only to mitigate the challenges posed by environmental noise and other distortions but also to enrich the overall communication experience, making every spoken word as comprehensible and pleasant to the ear as it was intended to be. The whole dimension of communications has been changed by the rapid growth of technology. Today people are more interested in hands-free communication, which makes use of loud speaker and high gain microphone, in place of the old modelled wired telephone. The main advantage of wireless system is that, more than one person can participate in conversation while freely moving in the room.

A. Speech Enhancement

The main objective of speech enhancement technique is to improve the quality and minimize the loss in intelligibility of the signal and listener fatigue. The basic overview is shown in Figure 1. spoken enhancement is the process of increasing the clarity and intelligibility of a spoken signal. This procedure employs a variety of signal processing techniques targeted at reducing or eliminating undesirable noise from the speech signal, lowering reverberation, and separating mixed speech signals to make the speech clearer and more comprehensible to listeners. The primary goals of speech enhancement are to improve the naturalness and pleasantness of the speech signal (quality) and make the speech more understandable, or easier to understand.

Fig. 1: Basic Speech Enhancement System

Continuous improvement of communication and multimedia systems has led to the widespread use of speech recording and processing devices, e.g., mobile phones, speech recognition tools. In most practical situations, these devices are being used in environments where undesirable background noise exists. Degraded speech can cause problems for both mobile communication and speech recognition systems. Nowadays, all the people use the communication devices almost as a primary good: telephones, mobiles, internet and the customers demand a high coverage and quality. The following Applications of Speech Enhancement:

- Speech enhancement is used in the recording and broadcast industries to improve audio track quality by reducing noise and increasing clarity, which is essential for podcasts, news broadcasts, and music production.
- Forensic Audio Analysis: Speech enhancement is used in forensic investigations to clarify audio recordings, allowing speech to be understood even when it is covered by noise or distortion.
- Speech augmentation can help language learning programs and educational software deliver clear pronunciations and instructions, especially in loud learning contexts.
- Telecommunications: Speech enhancement is vital in mobile and telephone services to ensure clear communication in noisy locations like streets, airports, and crowded areas.
- Hearing aids and cochlear implants use speech enhancement to increase the voice signal above background noise, allowing users with hearing impairments to better understand speech.
- Speech enhancement is used to increase the identification accuracy of voice-controlled systems, such as smart home devices, virtual assistants (e.g., Siri, Alexa), and in-car systems, by filtering out background noise and focusing on the speaker's voice.
- voice enhancement techniques aid in the delivery of intelligible voice during teleconferencing and Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) applications by minimizing echoes, noise, and interference.

2. ADAPTIVE FILTER

The basic idea of an adaptive noise cancellation algorithm is to pass the corrupted signal through a filter that tends to suppress the noise while leaving the signal unchanged. This is an adaptive process, which means it does not require a priori knowledge of signal or noise characteristics. Adaptive noise cancellation (ANC) efficiently attenuates low frequency noise for which passive methods are ineffective. Suppose an adaptive filter with a primary input $i(n)$, that is noisy speech signal $S(n)$ with additive noise $C(n)$. While the reference input is noise $r(n)$, which is correlated in some way with $C(n)$. If the filter output is $f(n)$, the output of the summer $O(n)$ is nothing but the error signal and it is written as, filter error $e = \{S(n) + C(n)\} - f(n)$.

Fig. 2: Adaptive filter with noise canceller

3. PROPOSED BLOCK DIAGRAM AND PROCESS

This project is all about the speech enhancement of voice signal using different adaptive filters. The speech signal is first mixed with a noise signal then it is modulated with two of the analog modulation techniques i.e. AM and FM; one at a time. Then AWGN is chosen as a communication channel in configuration with one of the modulation technique. Then at the receiver side demodulation is performed and filtered with adaptive filters. The same process is also done with Rician fading channel. The filters which are used are: LMS, NLMS and UNANR. The following block diagram gives the complete idea of the project. The major units are modulation, communication channel and adaptive filters. This project comprises of two types of input voice signal: stored voice signal and microphone voice signal.

Fig. 3: Simulation block of adaptive filter using communication channel

A. Process flow for a speech enhancement system

The block diagram depicts a process flow for a speech enhancement system that employs adaptive filters. Here's a thorough description of each block and the overall procedure:

Stored Voice/Microphone Voice: This block depicts two possible sources of the voice signal. The term "stored voice" refers to previously recorded voice data, whereas "microphone voice" refers to real-time audio data acquired.

Read the voice data: This step requires retrieving the voice data from one of the two sources.

Read Noise: This block retrieves the stored noise data, which will be used to simulate a noisy environment for the speech signal.

Pre-processing of data: Prior to actual processing, voice data is pre-processed, which may include normalization, filtering, or segmenting the signal into manageable chunks.

Noise addition: To imitate a loud environment, the "Read Noise" block's noise is added to the pre-processed voice stream. This is when the clean speech stream is purposefully damaged to test the effectiveness of noise reduction techniques.

Modulation AM/FM: The noisy voice signal is then modified with either Amplitude Modulation (AM) or Frequency Modulation. Modulation is the process of changing one or more features of a periodic waveform, known as the carrier signal, using a modulating signal, which usually carries information to be sent.

AWGN/Rician: Following modulation, the signal is routed through either an Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) or a Rician fading channel.

Demodulation AM/FM: After transmission across the channel, the received signal is demodulated to separate the voice signal from the carrier, thereby reversing the modulation process.

Adaptive Filters (LMS, NLMS, and UNANR): The demodulated signal is then treated using adaptive filters. Three types of adaptive filters are demonstrated: Least Mean Squares (LMS), Normalized Least Mean Squares (NLMS), and Unbiased Nonlinear Acoustic Noise Reduction (UNANR). Each of these filters adjusts its coefficients in real time to reduce the difference between the filtered and desired signals (in this case, the original clean voice signal).

Calculate the parameters (RMSF and PSNR): After filtering, the system computes performance metrics including Root Mean Square Error (RMSF) and Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR). These measurements assess how effectively the adaptive filters improved the signal by comparing the filtered signal to the original clean signal.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performances of the adaptive filters are compared with respect to the variation in SNR (dB). The used modulation techniques are AM and FM and the considered channels are AWGN and Rician fading channel. Under speech enhancement techniques, for improving quality of adaptive filters a newly emerging filter is used i.e. UNANR. This filter's performance is compared with two traditionally used adaptive filters; LMS and NLMS. The above considered technologies have been combined using the MATLAB R2013a software (Version 8.1.0). Now for different cases for the performance evaluation, the selected range of SNR is -5 to 40. However there is no restriction of the SNR range. But, if SNR range increases then the simulation time will increase and the considered noise removal capability may decrease. It is necessary to evaluate the performance of the system, and PSNR and RMSE provide a base for comparing the performances of different filters. The used parameter as shown in table 1.

Transmission of Speech Signal with AM Modulation: The original speech signal is first mixed with background noise to simulate a real-life noisy environment. This composite signal is then modulated using Amplitude Modulation (AM). AM is a technique used in electronic communication, most commonly for transmitting information via a radio carrier wave. AM works by varying the strength of the carrier signal in proportion to the waveform being sent.

Rician Fading Channel: The modulated signal is then sent through a Rician fading channel. This type of channel is characterized by a dominant direct line-of-sight path between the transmitter and receiver, along with numerous other scattered paths caused by reflection, diffraction, and scattering. The Rician channel model adds both a direct signal component and a diffuse noise component to the transmitted signal, representing a more realistic environment where direct and reflected paths are present.

AM Demodulation at Receiver: At the receiver's side, the signal that has been altered by the Rician channel is demodulated using AM demodulation. This process is the reverse of modulation and is used to retrieve the original speech signal with added noise from the modulated carrier wave.

Adaptive Filtering: After demodulation, the speech signal, now containing both background and channel noise, is passed through an adaptive filter. The aim of the adaptive filter is to remove as much of the noise as possible and to recover the original speech signal to make it more intelligible and clear.

Table 1: Simulation Parameters

Technology	Speech enhancement
Channel	AWGN/ Rician
Modulation	AM/FM
Filter	LMS, NLMS and UNANR
SNR range	38dB to -2.5dB
Input signal	Online

A. FM with Rician fading channel

In this case FM is selected to transmit the whole speech signal after addition of background noise at the transmitter side. Rician fading channel is selected as a communication channel for transferring the speech signal. In Rician fading channel, channel noise gets added to the speech signal. At the receiver side first FM demodulation is performed then speech signal is passed through one of the adaptive filter. Firstly LMS filter is selected and PSNR and RMSE signal parameters are recorded. Secondly NLMS filter is selected for the same received demodulated speech signal. And at the last UNANR filter is selected for the same received demodulated speech signal. As shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Adaptive Filtering on FM with Rician Channel for Stored Voice

B. AM with Rician fading channel

In this case AM is selected to transmit the whole speech signal after addition of background noise at the transmitter side. Rician fading channel is selected as a communication channel for transferring the speech signal. In Rician fading channel, channel noise gets added to the speech signal. At the receiver side first AM demodulation is performed then speech signal is passed through one of the adaptive filter. Firstly LMS filter is selected and PSNR and RMSE signal parameters are recorded.

Fig. 5: Adaptive filtering on AM with Rician channel for stored voice

Secondly NLMS filter is selected for the same received demodulated speech signal. And at the last UNANR filter is selected for the same received demodulated speech signal. Graphs have been plotted to check the performance of the adaptive filters. Communication channel for transferring the speech signal. In Rician fading channel, channel noise gets added to the speech signal. At the receiver side first AM demodulation is performed then speech signal is passed through one of the adaptive filter. Firstly LMS filter is selected and PSNR and RMSE signal parameters are recorded. Secondly NLMS filter is selected for the same received demodulated speech signal. And at the last UNANR filter is selected for the same received demodulated speech signal. Graphs have been plotted to check the performance of the adaptive filters. As shown in Fig. 5.

5. CONCLUSION

From all the performed experiments it is apparent that NLMS and UNANR filter have better performance than adaptive LMS filters. When the online voice signal is taken as input to the speech enhancement system then UNANR performed slightly better than NLMS filter. Though UNANR takes little more time to filter speech signal from noise in comparison with LMS and NLMS but has better convergence rate than other two. As soon as the Signal to noise ratio in dB improves performances of the filters get improved and when background noise level gets increased then performances of LMS, UNANR and NLMS filters gets degraded.

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